

D6.2

Dissemination, Communication and Engagement Report (M18)

AUSTRALO

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Abstract

This document summarises the dissemination, communication, and engagement efforts implemented during DATAMITE's first 18 months (M1-M18). It includes an in-depth description of the project's visual identity, online platforms, promotional materials, events, publications, and networking strategies and activities aimed at building a substantial audience and stakeholder base.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, Stakeholders, Impact, DSSC, Ecosystem building

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope.....	11
1.2 Document Structure	12
2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy	13
2.1 Strategy Approach and Timeline.....	13
2.2 Engagement Framework.....	14
3 Communication and Dissemination Performance Review – KPIs	17
4 Communication & Dissemination Activities	19
4.1 Branding	19
4.1.1 Logo and Brand.....	19
4.1.2 Official Templates.....	20
4.2 Promotion Material	22
4.2.1 Printed Material	22
4.2.2 Multimedia Material	23
4.3 Digital Channels	24
4.3.1 DATAMITE Website	24
4.3.2 Social Media	28
4.3.3 Open Access Repository – ZENODO	32
4.3.4 DATAMITE’s Newsletter.....	33
4.4 Publications	34
4.4.1 Scientific Publications.....	34
4.4.2 Awareness Publications	35
4.4.3 Press Release	36
4.5 Events, Workshops and Webinars	37
4.5.1 Events.....	37
4.5.2 Workshops and Webinars	45

5	Coordination with the DSSC and related Data Spaces Strategy and Activities.....	48
5.1	Coordination Strategy	48
5.2	Activities	52
5.3	Next Steps.....	66
6	Ecosystem Development and Community Building Strategy and Activities.....	68
6.1	Engagement Strategy	68
6.1.1	Target Stakeholders	69
6.1.2	Ecosystem Building Strategy Phases	70
6.2	Key Strategy Activities during the Initial Phase.....	71
6.2.1	Collection of Information from Existing EU DATA Projects	71
6.2.2	Market Analysis	74
6.2.3	Leveraging on the Networks of the DATAMITE Partners	75
6.2.4	Community of Developers and Open-Source DATAMITE	75
6.3	Key Strategy Activities during Development – Phase 2.....	80
6.3.1	Contribution to Strategic Events.....	80
6.3.2	Synergies with EU Funded Projects related to Data Monetization	81
6.3.3	Engagement with Community of Developers and Open-Source	84
7	Next Steps	86
8	Conclusions	87

List of figures

Figure 1. Dissemination Plan Phases	13
Figure 2. DATAMITE Stakeholder Groups	15
Figure 3. DATAMITE's D&C Monitoring Tool.....	18
Figure 4. DATAMITE Logo in Different Formats	19
Figure 5. DATAMITE's Branding Colours	20
Figure 6. DATAMITE's Presentation Template	21
Figure 7. DATAMITE's Document Template	21
Figure 8. Booth Background.....	22
Figure 9. DATAMITE's Roll-up.....	23
Figure 10. Poster	22
Figure 11. Trifold Brochure.....	23
Figure 12. DATAMITE's Promotional Video.....	23
Figure 13. DATAMITE Website	25
Figure 14. DATAMITE Website Analytics	26
Figure 15. DATAMITE Website Visitors by Country	26
Figure 16. DATAMITE Activities Section.....	27
Figure 17. DATAMITE LinkedIn Page.....	28
Figure 18. Top 3 LinkedIn Posts	29
Figure 19. DATAMITE X/Twitter Page	30
Figure 20. DATAMITE YouTube Channel.....	31
Figure 21. DATAMITE's Open Repository (ZENODO)	32
Figure 22. 1 st DATAMITE's Newsletter	33
Figure 23. DATAMITE's Joint Press Release	36
Figure 24. Featured Events on the Website.....	44
Figure 25. DSSC Network of Stakeholders, Source: DSSC meeting	49
Figure 26. Network of Stakeholders Exchange.....	49
Figure 27. DSSC Engagement Strategy	51
Figure 28. DSSC Blueprint Offer	53

Figure 29. Morphological Analysis enables Categorization	55
Figure 30. DATAMITE Monetization Strategy Overview	56
Figure 31. External and Internal Layers in the DATAMITE General Architecture.....	57
Figure 32. Screenshot During the Data Quality in Data Spaces Session – DATAMITE's Approach	58
Figure 33. The Three Phases of the Ecosystem Development Strategy	70
Figure 34. Interactive Ecosystem Navigator Front-end.....	72
Figure 35. Interactive Ecosystem Navigator - European Projects filtered by Research Topic and Organisation Type.....	72
Figure 36. Organisations Ranked by Amount of Funding Landed on EU DATA Projects (2010- 2023) ...	73
Figure 37. Ecosystem Tool - Most Frequent Partners in European DATA Consortia.....	74
Figure 38. The Ecosystem Tool Map for European DATA Coordinators & Participants	74
Figure 39. The Eclipse Project Creation Process	76
Figure 40. Eclipse Research Labs Phases	79
Figure 41. DATAMITE Open-Source Timeline.....	80
Figure 42. Snapshots from EU Project Synergies during Events	82
Figure 43. Monthly Alliance Coordination Meetings.....	83
Figure 44. Projects Participating in the Alliance Activities	83
Figure 45. Alliance's Main Pillars	84
Figure 46. The DATAMITE Eclipse Labs Repository	85

List of tables

Table 1. Target Stakeholders	16
Table 2. Outreach Activities Scope	16
Table 3. DATAMITE's KPIs	17
Table 4. Scientific Publications	34
Table 5. DATAMITE Website Published Articles.....	35
Table 6. List of Events	44
Table 7. List of Workshops	47
Table 8. Expert Groups and Participants.....	52
Table 9. Thematic Groups and Participants	54

Table 10. Data Spaces and Participants 59

Table 11. Ecosystem and Community Building KPIs (M36) 68

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AD4GD	AgriDataSpace for the Green Deal
ADRA	Ai Data Robotics Association
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEADS	Common European Agricultural Data Space
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D&C	Communication & Dissemination
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DIHs	Digital Innovation Hubs
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
DSBA	Data Spaces Business Alliance
DSSC	Data Space Support Centre
DoA	Description of Action
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EC	European Commission
ECA	Eclipse Contributor Agreement
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EDWG	Eclipse Dataspace Working Group
EDWIN	eDWIN Advisory Platform - Wielkopolska Agricultural Advisory Center
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPL	Eclipse Public License
EU	European Union
eSAAM	Eclipse Security, AI, Architecture and Modelling Conference
GA	General Assembly
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
OCX	Open Community Experience
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SME	Small Medium Enterprises
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TEMS	Trusted European Media Data Spaces
TG	Thematic Group
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable serves as an updated and detailed assessment of DATAMITE's activities designed for **Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement** objectives. The original structure of this strategy was initially defined in DATAMITE's **Impact Master Plan (D6.1)**¹ during the project's early phases. This document offers a detailed summary of the Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, schedule, tools, and approach, along with comprehensive descriptions of all the actions implemented thus far to achieve the intended goals:

- Effectively promote the project and its outcomes in various public forums such as events, conferences, and webinars by participating or hosting.
- Ensure accurate communication and dissemination of available results to scientific communities in the data management and data monetisation fields as well as the general public, presenting DATAMITE's accomplishments in an easily understandable and widely accessible manner for both expert and non-expert target groups.
- Sustain dedicated communication channels that are active, engaging, and informative in updating our target audiences about our goals, achievements, and daily activities within DATAMITE.
- Coordinate with the to ensure alignment between DATAMITE and the Digital Europe programme by hosting and participating in regular joint meetings that foster collaboration and support the development and deployment of the Common European Data Spaces, ensuring a seamless integration of DATAMITE into the data spaces ecosystem.
- Efficiently coordinate the efforts across partners to target the right stakeholder engagement activities. These were mainly focused on identify potential stakeholders through past and on-going EU funded projects, cluster activities with funded projects on the same call as DATAMITE, and the initial steps for engaging the community of developers with DATAMITE's open-source outcomes.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8093984>

1 Introduction

The success of disruptive innovation in the long term greatly hinges on its ability to raise awareness effectively and generate substantial engagement. By crafting and implementing efficient dissemination, communication and engagement strategies, the outcomes and accomplishments can create widespread recognition and endure well beyond the project's initial phase. Hence, the robust DATAMITE's dissemination and communication strategy focuses its efforts to engage key stakeholders actively in the project, fostering a dedicated community capable of creating networking opportunities for future advancements and informing the general public about the impact of the project's outcomes on the European DATA Ecosystem.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

This report, identified as **D6.2 - Dissemination, Communication, and Engagement Interim Report**, is situated within the framework of DATAMITE's WP6 - Outreach, Exploitation, and Collaboration, specifically under task **T6.1 - Dissemination and Communication, Task 6.4 Coordination with the Data Spaces Support Centre and related Data Spaces** and **Task 6.5 - Ecosystem Development and Community Building**. It provides an overview of all significant communication, dissemination, community building, engagement with the DSSC and all related activities undertaken during the **project's initial 18 months**. The report includes an analytical evaluation of the performance of digital channels, participation in physical and online events, and the publication of online articles and scientific publications.

The initial strategy for Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement was presented in deliverable **D6.1 - DATAMITE Impact Master Plan**, which was submitted in M6. The **D6.2** report showcases the progress of the project's outreach and engagement strategies and activities during the **first 18 months period (M1-M18)**. An update on this progress will be included in the upcoming **D6.3- Dissemination, Communication and Engagement final report**, which represents the project's conclusive report on Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement activities.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is organised as follows to align with these high-level objectives:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings are provided.
- **Section 1 Introduction:** Provides the deliverable's general context, scope and structure.
- **Section 2 Communication & Dissemination Strategy:** offering a comprehensive overview of the outreach activities, the digital channels and the digital and printed material.
- **Section 3 Communication & Dissemination Performance Review - KPIs:** presenting key performance metrics, including website traffic, social media engagement, publication downloads, and event participation, to assess the effectiveness of DATAMITE's outreach strategy.
- **Section 4 Communication & Dissemination Activities,** presenting the specific actions and highlights implemented.
- **Section 5 Coordination with the Data Spaces Support Centre and related Data Spaces strategy and activities:** showcasing the approach and the contributions with the Data Spaces Support Centre and relevant data spaces.
- **Section 6 Ecosystem Development and Community Building Strategy and Activities:** elaborating on efforts to identify and engage with relevant communities to foster ecosystem development and establish a foundation for long-term sustainability.
- **Section 7 Next Steps:** outlining the next steps and activities planned for the second half of the project.
- **Section 8 Conclusions:** summarising the key points of this deliverable.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Strategy Approach and Timeline

The communication and dissemination activities are being executed in three primary phases according to the strategy described in D6.1 – Impact Master Plan, each with distinct objectives and corresponding actions utilising appropriate channels. These phases were introduced and deliberated upon at the project's inception and refined progressively to align with DATAMITE's evolving priorities. During the period M1-M18 the activities of the Analysis and Increase impact phases were successfully implemented steadily enhancing DATAMITE's visibility, engagement and impact with its stakeholders.

Figure 1. Dissemination Plan Phases

Regularly monitoring the impact on performed activities and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication strategy is crucial for the project's success. During the initial half of the project, AUSTRALO, as the coordinator of WP6, consistently coordinated and tracked the dissemination and communication activities. This has enabled the consortium to identify and adapt to any potential deviations and enhance the strategy's effectiveness by applying corrective and mitigation measures when necessary.

- **During the first six months**, the activities were focused on developing its visual identity, setting up communication and dissemination channels, and initially mapping stakeholders.

- **From M6 to M12**, the activities were shifted its focus towards building a recognisable digital presence, initiating conversations with related initiatives, connecting with other EU-funded projects and the DSSC, participating in events/fairs, and creating additional promotional materials and long-form articles to reach a wider audience.
- **From M12 to M18**, the activities aimed to increase DATAMITE's visibility with its involvement in events, publications, and social media campaigns. During this phase, the project has also worked on refining its outreach proposition and engagement strategy, as well as developing high-quality interviews and promotional materials. As of the creation of this deliverable, the main goal is to continue strengthening DATAMITE's presence in digital channels, reinforcing its core messages, and linking them to upcoming results. Additionally, the project aims to fortify its engagement with the DSSC and the broader ecosystem through participation in events and working groups.

Over the course of these 18 months, the project has managed to amplify its online presence, with a significant number of 1,418 followers on social media, a steady weekly content stream with 536 posts in social media, 51 blog entries and 14 ZENODO repository entries are generating +800 downloads overall. This promotional effort has been complemented by increased participation in key events, conferences, and webinars as shown in section 4.5, as well as a strong commitment to dissemination, as evidenced by the consortium's six peer-reviewed and conference publications as shown in section 4.4.1.

Throughout this process, the project has maintained a harmonised branding identity and a comprehensive set of promotional materials in print (Roll-up, Poster, Brochures) and digital formats (Videos, Clips, Presentations) to support its communication and outreach activities.

This deliverable report, in sections 4-6, describes all outcomes and results of the Dissemination, Communication and engagement activities for the first 18 months of the project. They will be updated for the D6.3 Dissemination, Communication and Engagement final report in month 36.

2.2 Engagement Framework

To effectively promote DATAMITE and encourage stakeholder engagement, it is crucial to identify and understand the motivation and ambitions of the target audience. Recognising the influential roles that different stakeholders play in the value chain is vital for developing successful Dissemination and Communication Plans. From the project's inception, we have been developing a comprehensive Stakeholder Ecosystem database to map the diverse stakeholders relevant to

the DATAMITE project. As outlined in D6.1, during the initial six-month project phase, we identified key stakeholders to engage with, as illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2. DATAMITE Stakeholder Groups

Stakeholder Type	Data Stakeholders	Technology Providers	Partnership & Networks	Social Innovators	Policy Makers	Society
ADRA			X			
AI Engineers		X				
BDVA			X			
Data Aggregators	X					
Data Brockers	X					
Data Consumers	X					
Data Providers	X					
Data Scientists		X				
Digital Education Providers				X		
DSBA			X			
DSSC			X			
EIT Digital			X			
EOSC			X			
EU DIHs			X			
European Commission					X	
GAIA-X			X			

Stakeholder Type	Data Stakeholders	Technology Providers	Partnership & Networks	Social Innovators	Policy Makers	Society
Infrastructure Providers		X				
Non-Specialised Media						X
Observatories/ Think Tanks					X	
Open-Source Bodies		X				
Platform/Service /App Developers		X				
Privacy, Security, Legal Agencies					X	
Public Agencies					X	
Regulators					X	
Society						X
SSH & Ethical Researchers				X		
Standardisation Bodies		X				
UX Researchers				X		

Table 1. Target Stakeholders

As a subsequent step, from Month 6 to Month 18, DATAMITE prioritised stakeholder awareness and engagement through a range of targeted initiatives. These efforts focused on disseminating project information and fostering stakeholder participation via various activities, including newsletters, social media campaigns, event participation, workshop organisation, and content creation on the project website.

The table below provides a comprehensive overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities employed to educate and involve stakeholders in the project.

ACTIVITY	SCOPE
Events/workshops organised/participated	Thanks to these activities, the consortium could present the project to various stakeholders, inform them about our activities, and gather feedback.
Scientific publications	To reach a more technical audience, emphasising RTOs and academia, to share the knowledge acquired by the project and its future applications.
Newsletters & awareness publications	To constantly inform our community about the project advancements and achievements.

Table 2. Outreach Activities Scope

3 Communication and Dissemination

Performance Review – KPIs

The table below presents the comprehensive list of DATAMITE's impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the current updated targets. **Section 3** contains a detailed breakdown of the project's KPIs.

Category	Reported M18	Target KPI (M36)	Indicator
Website Traffic	160	300	No. visitors/month
Social media	1418 110k	3000 200k	Size of the Community Number of impressions
Non-Scientific Articles	51	50	Awareness Publications
Open Access Downloads	828	1000	No. of downloads (total)
Webinars Workshops	7	25 1000	No. of Webinars / Workshops No. of Registrations / Participants
Conferences & Events	15	30	No. of Events participated.
Newsletters	10	15	No. of newsletters contributed/released.
Videos	2	3	No. of videos
Peer-Reviewed Publications		10	Scientific Publications in Journals
	6	10	Scientific Publications in Conferences
Insight Paper	0	1	Publication oriented to policymakers on the deployment of the Common European Data Spaces.

Table 3. DATAMITE's KPIs

Coordination resources:

To ensure effective tracking of all dissemination and communication activities, we created a customised **monitoring tool** (Spreadsheet) that consolidates all actions (planned and executed) within the DATAMITE framework, enabling us to measure KPI achievements and monitor partner involvement.

Figure 3. DATAMITE's D&C Monitoring Tool

To facilitate seamless internal communication, which is essential for successfully implementing our dissemination and communication strategy, a dedicated channel on [Slack](#) instant messaging platform has been established, the project's internal chat platform, ensuring effective collaboration and information sharing. Monthly Work Package 6 meetings are organised by AUS, to ensure all partners remain informed and aligned on related activities.

4 Communication & Dissemination Activities

During the first 18 months of the project, dissemination and communication efforts focused on two key areas:

- Facilitating open access to project results for the stakeholders (Dissemination)
- Promoting project activities visibility and online presence (Communication)

This report highlights the core activities undertaken by the project, focusing on:

- Digital outreach through the project website, social media, and open-access repository
- Development of promotional materials
- Publication of newsletters, online articles, and scientific journals
- Participation in and organisation of events and workshops
- Collaborative initiatives with stakeholders

4.1 Branding

A strong brand identity is crucial for the DATAMITE project. It enables the project to establish a recognisable and consistent visual presence, fostering a sense of community and cohesion among partners and stakeholders. By maintaining a consistent visual and identity, the DATAMITE project can effectively communicate its values, goals, and achievements while differentiating itself in the research and innovation landscape.

4.1.1 Logo and Brand

Figure 4. DATAMITE Logo in Different Formats

MAIN PALETTE

DARK BLUE

CMYK 100 / 100 / 26 / 24
WEB #272362
RGB 39 35 98

MEDIUM BLUE

CMYK 88 / 77 / 0 / 0
WEB #0000FF
RGB 0 0 255

ORANGE

CMYK 0 / 50 / 99 / 0
WEB #F7931E
RGB 247 147 30

GRADIENT 01

GRADIENT 02

SUPPORTING PALETTE

DARK GREY

CMYK 0 / 0 / 0 / 60
WEB #666666
RGB 102 102 102

PURPLE

CMYK 75 / 98 / 1 / 0
WEB #662D91
RGB 102 45 145

LIGHT GREY

CMYK 0 / 0 / 0 / 30
WEB #b3b3b3
RGB 179 179 179

PANTONE ALTERNATIVE PALETTE

PANTONE 293C

PANTONE 1375C

Figure 5. DATAMITE's Branding Colours

A comprehensive branding guidelines document was shared with all DATAMITE partners to ensure a unified visual identity. This internal document provided a single reference point for consistent branding and facilitated a cohesive visual presence across all partners.

4.1.2 Official Templates

To further reinforce the project's visual identity, official templates for presentations, reports, and other documents were developed and shared with all DATAMITE partners. This enables a standardised and professional appearance across all project-related materials and communications.

Figure 6. DATAMITE’s Presentation Template

Figure 7. DATAMITE’s Document Template

4.2 Promotion Material

Effective promotional materials—both printed and digital—are crucial for DATAMITE's success. They enable the project to reach a broader audience, create awareness, and foster engagement. By developing compelling materials, DATAMITE can efficiently communicate its vision, objectives, and achievements to stakeholders, contributing to the project's long-term impact and sustainability.

4.2.1 Printed Material

Figure 8. Booth Background

DATAMITE's booth background features a modern design, showcasing a stylised data-driven landscape with interconnected nodes, symbolising the project's mission to unleash the data monetisation potential, accompanied by key information, partner logos, website URL, and social media links. The project's roll-up, poster, and brochure are used during physical events such as conferences, fairs, and exhibitions, and they include additional key information and project objectives. All printed materials are also located in the [open Repository DATAMITE community \(ZENODO\)](#) for easy access and increased visibility.

The roll-up poster is divided into three main sections: a top header, a middle 'OUR OBJECTIVES' section, and a bottom 'OUR TEAM' section.

Top Header: Features the DATAMITE logo (a stylized 'd' with vertical bars) and the text 'datamite'. Below the logo, the main theme is 'DATA Monetization, Interoperability, Trading & Exchange.' To the right, there are three social media links: 'DATAMITE-HORIZON.EU', '@DATAMITE_EU', and '@DATAMITE'. The central text reads 'Unleashing the Monetisation Potential' and 'DATAMITE helps EU companies to better govern and monetize data by delivering a modular open-source framework in the form of software modules, training, and business materials for European companies.'

Middle Section: OUR OBJECTIVES

- DEVELOP:** an open-source framework that enhances how companies manage and exchange data, boosting monetization.
- CREATE:** a Data Sharing module with tools for seamless data sharing and trading, focusing on data compatibility and control.
- SUPPLY:** a set of open-source modules for data governance, quality, and security that is easy to integrate into current systems.
- STRENGTHEN:** European companies by providing models, indicators, and training resources for better data monetization.
- PUT DATAMITE INTO ACTION:** By testing its performance in situations and data-sharing scenarios.

Bottom Section: OUR TEAM

This section displays a grid of logos for the project's partners and sponsors, including:

- Co-funded by: I+D+i, AGREGO, CINECA, DIN, ITI, BENEVOLENTE, ECLIPSE, F4, Fraunhofer, GIDITEX, ALFA, INNOVATION, INTELLECTUAL, and others.
- Partners: ILMH, LOBA, OTC, PSNC, tecnolo, LCC, uk, and others.
- Funded by the European Union.

Figure 9. DATAMITE's Roll-up

DATA

Monetization,
Interoperability,
Trading &
Exchange.

Unleashing the Monetisation Potential

DATAMITE delivers a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

OUR OBJECTIVES

CREATE
a **Data Sharing module** including a collection of tools to share and trade data, focused on data interoperability and sovereignty, aimed at different targets including EU Portals and other European initiatives.

DEPLOY AND EVALUATE
the **achieved performance of DATAMITE** in six different pilots and data sharing environments, validating as well the technical training material.

DEVELOP
a **modular open-source framework** to improve the way companies manage and share their data to boost monetisation, supporting the European Initiative for Digital Commons.

PROVIDE
a **collection of open-source modules for data governance, quality and security** that can be easily integrated with existing systems and customized/extended with complementary algorithms and mechanisms.

IMPROVE
the **capabilities of EU companies** by providing models, indicators and training materials to upskill personnel and improve corporate strategies for monetisation.

SCAN ME

WWW
DATAMITE-HORIZON.EU

 @DATAMITE_EU

 @DATAMITE

OUR TEAM

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 10. Poster

Figure 11. Trifold Brochure

4.2.2 Multimedia Material

A visual identity for [video animation](#) and multimedia content was created based on DATAMITE’s brand and located on [DATAMITE’s YouTube channel](#). The project promotes events and online communities.

Figure 12. DATAMITE’s Promotional Video

4.3 Digital Channels

To maintain audience interest, the Dissemination and Communication team has developed targeted campaigns and storytelling content on [LinkedIn](#) and [X/Twitter](#), covering a diverse range of topics, including:

- Events
- Announcements
- Publications
- Research and Innovation Objectives
- Use Cases
- Meet the People behind DATAMITE
- Meet the DATAMITE team
- International Women's Day
- Women in Science
- Generic dissemination campaign of the project's channels: website, social media, newsletter
- Work Packages' target
- Data Protection Day
- Newsletters
- Achievements
- Project anniversaries/General Assemblies

4.3.1 DATAMITE Website

Project website	https://datamite-horizon.eu/
------------------------	---

The DATAMITE project website, from its first release, in Month 3 (March 2023), has been continuously improved to serve as a central hub, featuring the initiative's core concepts, methodology, news, outcomes, and results from our pilot projects. The website undergoes regular updates, with a steady stream of fresh content added monthly. By Month 18, we had published 51 news articles, averaging over 3 blog posts per month. Additionally, updates have been made to the website's content and team information as necessary, ensuring the stakeholders are always up to date with the project's progress.

Figure 13. DATAMITE Website

A review of Google Analytics metrics provides insight into the project's online presence in terms of website performance. The figures below represent aggregated totals from the launch of the DATAMITE website in March 2023 to the current date, covering the 18-month period. During this

period, the website has attracted a notable following, with 2564 visitors, and 5713 page views, averaging approximately 357 views per month.

Figure 14. DATAMITE Website Analytics

Figure 15. DATAMITE Website Visitors by Country

A dedicated [activities section](#) has been created on the DATAMITE website to showcase all articles, news, events, and deliverables. Users can easily filter the content by categories as shown in **Figure 16**:

Figure 16. DATAMITE Activities Section

4.3.2 Social Media

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/datamite/>

DATAMITE's LinkedIn community has 500 followers. DATAMITE's LinkedIn page has seen significant engagement, with 71527 post impressions, 2421 page and profile views, and an impressive +7520 post video views. In terms of content, the most popular posts have garnered considerable attention, revealing a diverse range of interests among the audience.

Figure 17. DATAMITE LinkedIn Page

Notably, both technical and social aspects of the project have received equal support, as evidenced by the following posts:

Figure 18. Top 3 LinkedIn Posts

X/Twitter https://x.com/DATAMITE_EU

Among DATAMITE's social media platforms, X/Twitter is the most popular channel, boasting a community of 918 followers and 38 920 post impressions. Similar to the approach on LinkedIn,

the Dissemination and Communication team has implemented a diverse content strategy on X/Twitter, scheduling almost daily posts and exploring various themes through targeted social media campaigns. Notably, the highest-performing tweet, with over 500 impressions was the [Women in Science Day](#), indicating that the X/Twitter audience responds well to video content featuring project partners. Building on this success, the strategy for the project's second phase will focus on creating more human-centred content highlighting the technical progress made in the project.

Figure 19. DATAMITE X/Twitter Page

YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/@DATAMITEHORIZONEU-rj6ke>

The DATAMITE project's YouTube channel serves as a central hub for all video content, providing a dedicated space for project-related videos. Following a strategic promotional approach, the channel has yielded the following results:

- Total videos uploaded: 9
- Total views: 519
- Total watch time: 8.6 hours

Figure 20. DATAMITE YouTube Channel

The DATAMITE project has established a solid online presence on X/Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, boasting a collective following of 1440 followers/subscribers across these three platforms. Social media has proven to be a valuable tool for directly engaging with the project's broader audience, connecting with key initiatives, and showcasing DATAMITE's accomplishments in publications, events, and partner initiatives.

4.3.3 Open Access Repository – ZENODO

In alignment with the European Commission's guidelines on Open Science, DATAMITE ensures open and unrestricted access to a wide range of project resources, including peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, brand assets, and other materials generated throughout the project. A dedicated ZENODO community and repository have been established to facilitate this open access approach, where various types of publications (such as articles, posters, and more) and press releases are made available. Furthermore, all public deliverables will be uploaded to both the [ZENODO repository](#) and the [project website](#), pending validation by the European Commission., pending validation by the European Commission.

The screenshot displays the ZENODO repository interface for the DATAMITE HORIZON EUROPE community. The top navigation bar includes a search bar, 'Communities', and 'My dashboard'. Below the header, the community name 'DATAMITE HORIZON EUROPE' is shown with a 'New upload' button. The main content area shows 8 results found, sorted by 'Oldest'. The results are filtered by 'Open' access status. The first result is 'DATAMITE Joint Press Release' (January 31, 2023) with 206 views and 307 downloads. The second result is 'DATAMITE Logo' (February 7, 2023) with 87 views and 56 downloads. The third result is 'The DATAMITE first Newsletter' (March 31, 2023) with 69 views and 70 downloads. The interface also features filters for Versions, Access status, Resource types, and Subjects.

Figure 21. DATAMITE's Open Repository (ZENODO)

Our strategic approach to promoting the project's results has yielded positive outcomes, with the 14 documents uploaded to ZENODO reaching over 700 views by the 18-month mark.

4.3.4 DATAMITE's Newsletter

The project's newsletters have proven to be a straightforward yet effective means of disseminating project results and updates to stakeholders. Over the first 18 months, the consortium published five newsletters, with a scheduled release plan of at least three newsletters per year.

The released newsletters include:

- **Newsletter 1:** released on 31/03/2023 ([Link](#))
- **Newsletter 2:** released on 04/07/2023 ([Link](#))
- **Newsletter 3:** released on 04/10/2023 ([Link](#))
- **Newsletter 4:** released on 21/12/2023 ([Link](#))
- **Newsletter 5:** released on 11/04/2024 ([Link](#))

Figure 22. 1st DATAMITE's Newsletter

Each newsletter's content is carefully crafted to maintain reader engagement. The newsletters are distributed to 297 subscribers via [Brevo](#) and [LinkedIn](#). They can also be accessed on the project website ([Activities > News](#)) and the Zenodo repository.

Furthermore, DATAMITE expanded its reach by being featured in multiple external newsletters, such as ZSI ([April 2023](#)), ITI ([May 2023](#)), Eclipse ([July 2023](#)), OTE, and AUSTRALO thereby broadening its audience and engaging with a wider range of stakeholders.

4.4 Publications

4.4.1 Scientific Publications

DATAMITE, from M1 to M18, published the following scientific publications:

Category	Title	Platform	Status	Open Access
Conference Paper	Data Trading and Monetization: Challenges and Open Research Directions	International Conference on Future Networks & Distributed Systems	Published	https://zenodo.org/records/10255045
Conference Paper	Market Analysis of a Data Platform in the European Data Ecosystem	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Accepted	Embargo until 27/06/2025 (abstract available)
Conference Paper	Data Monetization Opportunities and Challenges: The European Landscape by DATAMITE	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Accepted	Embargo until 27/06/2025 (abstract available)
Conference Paper	Boosting Data Monetisation with DATAMITE	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Accepted	Embargo until 27/06/2025 (abstract available)
Conference Paper	Scalable Data Profiling for Quality Analytics Extraction	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Accepted	Embargo until 27/06/2025 (abstract available)
Conference Paper	A Network-based Intrusion Detection System based on widely used Cybersecurity Datasets and State of the Art ML techniques	International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	Accepted	Embargo until 27/06/2025 (abstract available)

Table 4. Scientific Publications

4.4.2 Awareness Publications

Since the project's beginning at M01, the DATAMITE consortium has been active and enthusiastic about creating engaging, non-technical online content. By M18, the project had published on all digital channels over 51 blog entries and over 530 awareness posts. These articles feature visual highlights and quotes from various project activities. To maintain audience interest and stakeholder engagement, the project adopted a campaign series approach to diversify the content, share compelling stories, and convey the knowledge gained throughout the project.

Table 4 presents the published [DATAMITE website articles](#) until M18:

Title	Date
DATAMITE Project host its kick-off meeting in Valencia	19/01/2023
Welcome! We invite you to make some puzzles!	03/02/2023
Women In Science: Meet Daniela Greven	11/02/2023
How will we contribute to the EU Year of skills?	30/03/2023
Project cluster: HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-04	30/03/2023
Use Case: Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange	03/07/2023
How DATAMITE will contribute to unlock the potential of data	03/07/2023
Use Case: Connecting eDWIN to data markets	28/09/2023
Happy "back to school"!	28/09/2023
DATAMITE and the development of common EU data spaces	04/10/2023
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Santiago Cáceres (ITI)	15/11/2023
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Vasso Apostolopoulou (OTE)	04/12/2023
Time flies: a year of DATAMITE as seen from every WP	20/12/2023
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Samarkhel-Khan Yahya (DIN)	08/01/2024
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Ricardo Almeida Henriques (E-REDES)	07/02/2024
Women in Science Day: we are proud to be women scientists	11/02/2024
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Marko Turpeinen (1001 Lakes)	25/03/2024
Use Case: Offering Data to Service Providers with DataSpaces	10/04/2024
Meet the people behind DATAMITE: Mariano Playa Andreu (IDSA)	18/06/2024

Table 5. DATAMITE Website Published Articles

4.4.3 Press Release

The DATAMITE project has published a joint press release, effectively disseminating key project information to a wider audience. To maximise its impact and visibility, this report is made publicly available through the open repository [ZENODO](#), as well as on the [project's official website](#).

31st January 2023

Press Release

Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data

The consortium of **DATAMITE** — “**Data Monetization, Interoperability, Trading & Exchange**” — is proud to announce the official start of this European initiative, funded by the **European Commission** under the **Horizon Europe** research and innovation programme.

DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve Data Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels:

- **At internal level**, users will have tools to improve the quality and management of their data, the adherence to **FAIR** principles. They will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.
- **At external level**, users will boost their data sharing capabilities while keeping the control of their data, providing new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders.

DATAMITE delivers a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework, in the form of software modules, training and business materials.

The architecture envisioned for **DATAMITE** enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, **DATAMITE's solutions will function as catalysts to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.**

Figure 23. DATAMITE's Joint Press Release

4.5 Events, Workshops and Webinars

Events play a pivotal role in the DATAMITE project, serving as a key platform for knowledge sharing, networking, and collaboration among stakeholders. Through a series of organised events, including workshops, conferences, fairs and webinars, the project successfully fostered a sense of community and facilitated the exchange of ideas and expertise. These events not only enabled the dissemination of project results and advancements but also provided a unique opportunity for stakeholders to engage with the project's outcomes, offer feedback, and further shape the project's direction.

DATAMITE has been featured, co-organised, sponsored and participated in 15 events and 7 workshops/Webinars.

4.5.1 Events

Table 6 presents DATAMITE's participation and contribution in events until month 18 (June 2024):

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
ITM Industry Europe 2023	30/5/2023	Poznan, Poland	Panellist	2000
<p>The ITM Industry Europe 2023 trade fair took place from 30 May to 1 June, showcasing innovative products and services aligned with the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Centre (PSNC) participated in a panel discussion on SME support tools for Industry 4.0, highlighting the importance of collaboration between universities, research institutes, and companies. The DATAMITE project was featured as an example of successful cooperation between diverse organisations driving innovation in Industry 4.0.</p>				
DATA WEEK 23	13/06/2023	Luleå, Sweden	Panellist	250
<p>The Data Week 2023 event took place from 13-19 June in Luleå, Sweden, gathering the European Big Data and Data-Driven AI research and innovation communities to share knowledge and discuss common interests. During the event, the DATAMITE project (represented by ITI) participated in a session on "Technological Enablers for the Next-Level Data Economy" alongside three other Horizon</p>				

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
<p>Europe projects, showcasing its modular, open-source Framework for data monetisation. The session highlighted the importance of data quality and robust use cases in shaping the future of the data economy.</p>				
<p><u>Women in Tech Summit 2023</u></p>	<p>14-15/6/2023</p>	<p>Warsaw, Poland</p>	<p>Booth</p>	<p>5000</p>
	<p>The Perspektywy Women in Tech 2023 conference and career fair took place on 14-15 June in Warsaw, Poland. It featured 150 inspiring female speakers and countless tech talks and workshops. The DATAMITE project participated in the event alongside the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Centre (PSNC) booth, promoting diversity and equality in STEM fields. The event showcased leading topics in tech, including AI, machine learning, and digital ecology, and provided a platform for women in tech to share their experiences and achievements.</p>			
<p><u>National Field Days</u></p>	<p>3-5/6/2023</p>	<p>Sielinko, Poland</p>	<p>Booth, Workshop</p>	<p>70000</p>
<p>The National Field Days, Poland's largest industry event, took place from 3-5 June in Sielinko, featuring hundreds of companies and tens of thousands of visitors. The DATAMITE consortium (represented by WODR & PSNC) showcased innovative agricultural solutions, including the eDWIN application and planned DATAMITE developments, in the event's Innovation Zone. In addition, workshops for companies were held regarding the building blocks for the dataspace. The event was attended by high-profile guests, including the European Commissioner for Agriculture and the Polish Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development.</p>				

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
<u>EGI2023</u>	19-23/6/2023	Poznan, Poland	Presentation, booth	250

The DATAMITE project had a prominent presence at the conference, with a physical booth and participation in several sessions, including a presentation on the agriculture use case by WODR and a session on data spaces governance featuring ITI. A representative from WODR discussed the agriculture use case, while a representative from ITI presented an overview of DATAMITE's approach to data monetisation, interoperability, trading, and exchange. The project's

booth allowed attendees to learn more about DATAMITE's objectives and approach to better monetise European data.

<u>Forum Privatheit</u>	5-6/10/2023	Berlin, Germany	Poster	100
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ZSI presented the outcomes of a first stakeholder workshop conducted at the Consortium Meeting in Athens in June 2023 with a poster on the DATAMITE project. The workshop focused on stakeholders' visions of non-monetary benefits of data sharing and validated and expanded six relevant dimensions for non-monetary effects together with stakeholders from the project's pilot studies to drive forward the analysis of non-monetary aspects of data sharing.

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
EclipseCon 2023	16-19/10/2023	Ludwisbourg, Germany	Booth	500
<p>The DATAMITE project participated in EclipseCon 2023, a leading conference for developers, architects, and open-source business leaders organised by the Eclipse Foundation, a DATAMITE partner. At the event, DATAMITE was showcased at the Eclipse Research booth, displaying a poster and distributing flyers and stickers to attendees, generating significant interest among the developer community. The conference provided an ideal platform for DATAMITE to connect with over 460 attendees, including developers, architects, researchers, and managers, and share its vision with the Eclipse ecosystem.</p>				
European Big Data Value Forum 2023	25-27/10/2023	Valencia, Spain	Panellist, Booth, Avatar, Brochure	600
<p>The European Big Data Value Forum 2023 took place in Valencia, Spain, bringing together professionals, researchers, and policymakers to advance data and AI initiatives. DATAMITE participated in the event with a booth, promoting the project and exchanging ideas with experts. DATAMITE, in collaboration with sister projects PISTIS, UPCAST, and FAME, co-organized a session exploring AI, data trading, and interoperability in shaping the data economy. The session, moderated by IDC and ITI, featured expert speakers discussing innovations in data</p>				

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
<p>trading, monetisation, and exchange, as well as interoperability. The event provided a valuable opportunity for DATAMITE to connect with the European big data community and share its vision for the future of the data economy. OTE created a digital avatar of DATAMITE and placed it at the project’s booth, creating an engaging and interactive experience for attendees to learn more about the project's vision and objectives.</p>				
<p>InfoCom</p>	<p>14/12/2023</p>	<p>Athens, Greece</p>	<p>Presentation, Brochure, Avatar</p>	<p>1000</p>

The OTE hosted a session focused on DATAMITE at the 25th Infocom World 2023 Conference in Athens, featuring presentations on data monetisation, interoperability, trading, and exchange. The session, moderated by Hellenic Telecommunications Organization, included insights from ITI, Hellenic Telecommunications Organization, HEDNO, and CERTH on DATAMITE's contributions to European data monetisation. The DATAMITE booth, hosted by the IT Innovation Center of OTE Group, allowed partners HEDNO, ICCS, and AUSTRALO to introduce the project and provide additional information. Attendees engaged with partners and interacted with a digital avatar, serving as a "Digital Assistant" for the project.

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
<u>International Conference on Future Networks & Distributed Systems</u>	21-22/12/2023	Dubai, United Arab Emirates	Presentation	100

12:10-12:20 | [Data Trading and Monetization: Challenges and Open Research Directions](#) | CR-2002
Qusai Ramadan, Zeyd Boukhers, Muath AlShaikh, Christoph Lange, and Jan Jürjens

DATAMITE was present in the International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems (ICFNDS) which aims at addressing advances in research on distributed systems and future networks.

Specifically in the session titled "Data Trading and Monetization: Challenges and Open Research Directions" the University of Koblenz represented DATAMITE, sharing technical and organisational challenges affecting data monetisation and identifying areas in need of further research (Publication in **Table 4**), aiming to expand the boundaries of current knowledge by emphasising where research is currently limited or lacking.

<u>Data Spaces Symposium 2024 / DataWeek 2024</u>	12-14/03/2024	Frankfurt, Germany	Panellist	1000
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The Data Spaces Symposium, organised by DSSC and DSBA, featured the latest market-ready use cases and advanced technology solutions for data spaces. DATAMITE participated in the session "Navigating the Future of Data Monetisation" alongside five other Horizon Europe projects, exploring the multifaceted dimensions of data monetisation. ITI represented DATAMITE, sharing case studies and addressing challenges in data monetisation to make European companies and administrations key players in the data economy. The session facilitated a comprehensive dialogue on transforming data into economic assets, unlocking its value, and overcoming associated challenges.

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
<u>DataWeek 2024</u>	05/06/2024	Leuven, Belgium	Panellist	120
	<p>DataWeek 2024, organised by BDVA - Big Data Value Association, was held in Leuven, Belgium. DATAMITE was represented by ITI in the experts' discussion held within the session 'Data Value creation,' which shared the aim and the value of data monetisation.</p>			
<u>ISC 2024</u>	12-16/05/2024	Hamburg, Germany	Exhibitor	3500
<p>DATAMITE was represented by PSNC and was featured in the PSNC booth during International Supercomputing, that is focusing on HPC, ML, data analytics and quantum computing. The presentation of the DATAMITE has been shown on the stand to the visitors.</p>				
<u>Field Days 2024</u>	7-8.6.2024	Sielinko, Poland	Exhibitor	30000
	<p>DATAMITE was represented by WODR and PSNC and was featured in the common booth. The focus was on solutions for data sharing among companies and in the ecosystem.</p>			

Title	Date	Location	Contribution	Reach
Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI) Conference	27/6/2024	Corfu, Greece	5 Publications, Panel Discussion	100

DATAMITE made a significant impact at the Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI) Conference. Representatives from OTE, CERTH, ICCS, and UCC presented five notable publications (**Table 4**). Additionally, DATAMITE organized a panel discussion on data handling and monetization, moderated by AUS. Representatives from [6G-PATH](#), [AMBITIOUS](#), [Smart5Grid](#), [ELOQUENCE](#), [CyberSecDome](#) EU projects shared valuable insights on the challenges and significance of data handling strategies for EU organizations and companies.

Table 6. List of Events

A dedicated "[Events](#)" category in the project website's news section provides a one-stop portal featuring a comprehensive archive of all DATAMITE events and conferences.

Figure 24. Featured Events on the Website

4.5.2 Workshops and Webinars

Throughout the initial project phase, the DATAMITE team successfully organised or participated in a total of 7 workshops. This comprised 4 internal workshops held during the General Assembly meetings in Athens, Bologna and Poznan and one online workshop, which focused on discussing the exploitation activities and refining project innovations. Additionally, the team participated in 3 external workshops, further expanding its collaborative efforts.

Type	Title	Date	Contribution	Partner
Online Workshop	DSSC Get-to-know meeting	23/02/2023	Presentation	ITI
<p>ITI represented DATAMITE in this workshop organised by the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC). The event provided an excellent platform to establish connections with fellow coordinators and to learn about the various projects under the HORIZON-CL4-2021 and HORIZON-CL4-2022 DATA programs. The structured blocks allowed for fruitful exchanges and a better understanding of the synergies between our initiatives. During the session we presented the overall overview of the project (Mission and objectives), concrete expected contributions from DATAMITE to the European Common Data Spaces and expected needs for collaboration with data spaces and other initiatives.</p>				
Interactive Workshop	Focus group on benefits beyond monetarization	29/06/2023	Presentation & Hands-on	Consortium
<div style="display: flex; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="margin-left: 20px;"> <p>On the 29th of June 2023, ZSI conducted a focus group in Athens where consortium members engaged in insightful discussions regarding future scenarios that extend beyond the monetary benefits of the project. The workshop was aimed at exploring how each partner could derive additional value from their participation. Participants shared diverse perspectives, which were subsequently clustered to identify common themes and innovative approaches but also communicated the several issues and threads. The event fostered a deeper understanding on expectations beyond the monetary value, paving the way for the alignment of desk research and views from the pilots.</p> </div> </div>				

Type	Title	Date	Contribution	Partner
Workshop	AI, Data, Robotics Forum #ADRF23	8-9/11/2023	Panellist	UCC
<p>UCC represented DATAMITE in a panel discussion at a workshop with strategic partners and the EC, focusing on positioning the ecosystem of AI, Data, and Robotics. The session highlighted DATAMITE's role in constructing and linking the data ecosystem, showcasing the project's tools and capabilities. The discussion explored the project's potential to drive innovation and growth in the data economy.</p>				
Workshop	Data Monetization Maturity Model	21/11/2023	Presentation & Hands-on	Consortium
<p>A first workshop for the Data Monetization Maturity Model (DMMM) was conducted under the leadership of T4.3 in Bologna. 1001 Lakes presented general background about Maturity Modeling and also proposed a tailored process how to concretely come to the DMMM in DATAMITE.</p>				
Workshop	Pilots' architecture session	21/11/2023	Presentation & Hands-on	Consortium
		<p>Each of the pilot had separate dedicated workshop with the technical partners and technical architects of the systems to make sure pilot is aligned with the DATAMITE framework from one hand and that the architecture and planned developments address the needs of the pilots.</p>		

Type	Title		Date	Contribution	Partner
Webinar	Horizon Europe AI, Data & Robotics - Launch Event 2024		22/02/2024	Brochure and Video (Pitch)	ITI
			<p>The "Launch Event: showcasing the future of innovation in AI, Data, and Robotics" featured 54 projects funded under Horizon Europe calls, including DATAMITE. ITI presented the project's vision, objectives, and impact in a <u>2-minute video pitch</u>, highlighting DATAMITE's main objective and benefits for data monetisation. The event showcased the future of innovation in AI, Data, and Robotics, with projects from diverse domains sharing their projects in a concise and impactful manner.</p>		
Workshop	Data Maturity Model	16/05/2024	Presentation & Hands-on	Consortium	
<p>According to the plans, a core team of 1001 Lakes and FIR has formed itself and set up preparatory activities for a presence workshop in Poznan. In these preparatory activities a first criteria catalogue was proposed based on an extensive literature research. The core team agreed on seven dimensions to cluster the criteria catalogue and conducted a first online workshop on April 30, 2024, within WP4. The draft criteria catalogue was commented and consolidated during this workshop. Thereafter, the presence workshop was conducted based on this consolidated catalogue with the entire project plenary on May 16, 2024. Here, further input was requested from DATAMITE project members. As a result, a criteria revised criteria catalogue was finalized. In a post-processing to the workshop, the core team will consolidate this catalogue as a final first stable version.</p>					

Table 7. List of Workshops

5 Coordination with the DSSC and related Data Spaces Strategy and Activities

5.1 Coordination Strategy

The Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) is dedicated to fostering the creation of common data spaces that are sovereign, interoperable, and trustworthy for data sharing to enable data reuse within and across various sectors while upholding EU values and strengthening the European economy and society. As part of the Digital Europe Program and funded by the European Commission, their focus is on assisting the public sector and companies in establishing sovereign data spaces.

Furthermore, the DSSC aims to investigate the needs of data space initiatives, identify common requirements, and develop best practices. These efforts are directed towards accelerating the development of sovereign data spaces, which are essential for digital transformation across all domains. Leveraging the expertise of their consortium partners, they offer support to many data space initiatives, particularly with the goal of creating interoperable data spaces.

One of the key objectives of the DSSC is to establish a **Network of Stakeholders** that includes all relevant organizations and initiatives involved in the development of data spaces. This network comprises a diverse range of groups and individuals, offering a unique opportunity for collaboration and innovation. Participation in this network allows stakeholders to share insights, shape best practices, and contribute to the creation of interoperable and sovereign data spaces that support the European economy and society.

Moreover, the DSSC offers a range of assets to facilitate the creation and operation of data spaces. These include comprehensive guidelines, along with software tools and platforms that ensure secure and interoperable data sharing. The DSSC also provides educational resources to help stakeholders understand and implement data space concepts effectively.

Figure 25. DSSC Network of Stakeholders, Source: DSSC meeting

The **DSSC Strategic Stakeholder Forum (SSF)**, also referred to as the Strategic Stakeholder Group, is a think-and-do-tank that supports the DSSC in delivering on policy objectives. Together with the rest of the DSSC consortium partners, the SSF makes recommendations on the governance of the Support Centre’s assets, its evolution, and its sustainability. The SSF has an active, an advisory, and a strategic role at the DSSC.

Currently, the members of the Network of Stakeholders can be further involved in the DSSC activities by assigning representatives to join: The DSSC Thematic Groups and the DSSC Expert Groups.

Figure 26. Network of Stakeholders Exchange

DSSC Thematic Groups (TG) are community-driven forums fostering sharing and co-creating new knowledge. These groups are open to individuals representing initiatives or organisations

that have an exhibited relationship with the DSSC through participation in the Community of Practice, Strategic Stakeholder Forum and Liaisons & Collaborations. Currently, there are three active groups:

- Business of Data Spaces
- Governance of Data Spaces
- Technology of Data Spaces

DSSC Expert Groups are specialized, blueprint-driven teams focused on co-creating valuable assets for the DSSC. These groups consist of experts who have been selected to collaborate to develop guidelines, frameworks, and tools that support the creation and implementation of interoperable and sovereign data spaces.

Engagement Strategy for DATAMITE with DSSC

The primary goal of our engagement with the DSSC is to support the deployment of the Common European Data Spaces and develop a tight alignment between DATAMITE and the Digital Europe programme. We ensure that our project objectives are in line with those of Digital Europe and facilitate an effective knowledge exchange between the DSSC and DATAMITE.

To ensure effective collaboration and engagement with the DSSC, DATAMITE has identified different means of connection: participation of project representatives in DSSC Thematic Groups and the participation of some DSSC Expert Groups, and engagement in the Strategic Stakeholder Forum from the partners that are involved in various data space projects and initiatives as shown in **Figure 27**.

Figure 27. DSSC Engagement Strategy

Participation in Expert Groups: The main objective of participating in the expert groups is to actively contribute the insights and expertise of the DATAMITE project's expert partners, which can be highly relevant to the discussions within these groups. To facilitate this, some partners are involved in them. DATAMITE provides the relevant content about our findings, results, and progress, which could be beneficial for their involvement. This kind of participation manifests our vision and point of view of specific topics.

Participation in Thematic Groups: The main objectives of participating in the thematic groups are firstly, to receive knowledge and stay informed about the developments that other stakeholders are making in various projects or initiatives at the European level, which may be relevant for DATAMITE. Secondly, to present our key advancements and results to the other participants, thereby fostering potential future synergies.

To achieve this, we have mapped the DATAMITE partners involved in each of the three thematic groups in the following section. This mapping clarifies who is participating and, most importantly, help us to identify the main representatives for the project in each group. Thematic groups meet online monthly and co-design their agenda. This kind of participation enables us to share our results with other initiatives, as well as to learn and benefit from their experiences.

Involvement in Strategic Stakeholder Forum: The main goal is to serve as an ambassador to promote the DSSC's initiatives and objectives, as well as to influence and to stay informed about strategic decisions and directions related to data spaces.

5.2 Activities

In November 2023, during a T6.4 meeting, ITI introduced all participants to the various existing groups within the DSSC and outlined potential collaboration opportunities. Over the past 18 months, DATAMITE has actively engaged with the DSSC to advance the deployment of Common European Data Spaces and strengthen alignment with the Digital Europe programme. Our efforts have focused on fostering effective collaboration and knowledge exchange as follows:

Expert Groups Participants: In **Table 8**. Expert Groups and Participants we mapped the DATAMITE partners who have been invited to participate in any of the expert groups. This mapping allows us to identify the topics we are giving our vision to and provide our representants with relevant content about our knowledge, results, and progress, which could be beneficial for these groups and their other participants. It is important to emphasize that these participants were invited as representatives of their own institution/organization, but they will contribute with DATAMITE's project vision whenever it is valuable within the groups.

Expert Group	Expert Person / Organization
Governance Expert Group	Liliana Beltrán (ITI)
Rulebook Expert Group	Marko Turpeinen & Olli Pitkanen (1001 Lakes)
Legal Expert Group	Olli Pitkanen (1001 Lakes) Mark Dietrich (EGI)
Data Value Creation Expert Group	Andrea Manzi (EGI)
Data Sovereignty and Trust Expert Group	Valeria Ardizzone (EGI)
Subject Matter Expert Group	Javier Valiño (ECLIPSE Foundation)

Table 8. Expert Groups and Participants

These experts have contributed actively to the DSSC Expert Groups, sharing valuable insights and expertise on pertinent topics. They have been contributing to and discussing all the most

relevant topics in these areas for the development of the [Blueprint, both in its 0.5 and 1.0 versions](#), which have already been published. This blueprint serves as a comprehensive resource, offering essential information and guidance for initiating and successfully participating in data spaces. It includes a Starter Kit, a conceptual model, a glossary, and more advanced material organised into thematic building blocks. These blocks focus on business and organisational as well as technical subjects. Additionally, the blueprint provides instructions and material on deploying a data space and information about other data space initiatives that are currently running.

Figure 28. DSSC Blueprint Offer²

Thematic Groups Participants: We have mapped the DATAMITE partners who are attending each of the 3 thematic groups in **Table 9**. In this case, the participants are attending the group meetings on behalf of their organizations, but they are also contributing with DATAMITE's perspective.

Thematic Group	Partners participation	Main contact Point (Coordination)
Business Thematic Group	Liliana Beltrán (ITI)	Liliana Beltrán (ITI)

² <https://dssc.eu/page/knowledge-base>

Thematic Group	Partners participation	Main contact Point (Coordination)
	Elisa Cauche (EGI) Enrique Areizaga (TECNALIA)	
Governance Thematic Group	Liliana Beltrán (ITI) Mariano Blaya (IDSA) Alberto Berreteaga (TECNALIA)	Liliana Beltrán (ITI)
Technology Thematic Group	Jordi Arjona (ITI) Raul Palma (PSNC) Valentín Sánchez (TECNALIA) Alberto Berreteaga (TECNALIA)	Jordi Arjona (ITI)

Table 9. Thematic Groups and Participants

Engagement in Strategic Stakeholder Forum (SSF): We have reviewed and mapped the partners that are part of the forum: 1001 Lakes, EGI and ITI. These partners have been actively participating and involved in the meetings organized by the SSF throughout the 18-month period covered by this report.

FIR took part in the [DSSC Meeting on April 18th](#) concerning Data Products and Monetization. The results of Task 4.1 were presented and put into the context of the meeting. More specific: The Data Monetization Framework of Task 4.1 was presented regarding different strategies a company can pursue with Data Products and Services. This Framework has a questionnaire as a first step, where many of the previous discussion aspects of this meeting were found again. With the help of this questionnaire, a categorization of a company's current capabilities can be

made (**Figure 29**). This categorization leads to a visualization in the morphological analysis box, where different strategies have a pathway through the questionnaire. The questionnaire's result can be placed on top of this morphological box, helping the user identifying a potential Monetization Strategy to pursue.

Figure 29. Morphological Analysis enables Categorization

This categorization is a first step in helping the users find the right DATAMITE-tools for their specific business case. Due to the flexibility of the questionnaire and the analysis, a company can take advantage of properties of different strategies and does not need to stick to only one perspective.

These strategies have been elaborated in the form of “flashcards” where various information is depicted on a A4 sheet with the possible questionnaire’s answer on the backside. During the Meeting, a slide with the elaborated Monetization Strategies was shown to visualize the ways in which Data can generate revenue or reduce internal costs (**Figure 30**).

Strategy Overview

Figure 30. DATAMITE Monetization Strategy Overview

This presentation generated positive feedback by the DSSC developers and the meeting's guests, and they were interested to see the progress of this task in the future of DATAMITE.

TECNALIA has recently participated in the DSSC Technology Thematic Group session dedicated to data quality on June 13, 2024, describing the DATAMITE project, the development of the Data Quality, and the relationship with data spaces.

The session included presentations from data space initiatives about use cases where Data Quality is highlighted and from research projects building tools for Data Quality in data spaces.

A summary of the DATAMITE project was explained, as a project that aims to develop a technical framework for managing data and make it trustable and valuable, considering two layers, internal and external. **Figure 31** shows the DATAMITE general architecture and the components belonging to the external and internal layers.

Data Quality in Data Spaces: DATAMITE Approach

DATAMITE Framework

The DATAMITE project aims to develop a technical framework for managing data and make it trustable and valuable, considering two layers, internal and external.

Figure 31. External and Internal Layers in the DATAMITE General Architecture.

The Data Quality Module was explained to know the data, obtaining different indicators from the early stages of the data life cycle including data discovery and data ingestion. The reasoning behind states that knowing the status of their data, companies can see the value associated to them and subsequently how they will share them.

The presentation zoomed in the User defined Rules Generator component, a useful tool when it comes to evaluate the quality of the data in a particular company, considering the general dimensions and metrics could be not enough to represent the requirements defined by the data owner organization. To better define and manage the quality requirements that the companies need to achieve, the DATAMITE Data Quality Module provide this possibility for creating user defined rules and metrics through the before mentioned component.

The DDQV (DATAMITE DQV) was presented as an extension of the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV of the w3c group) to cover the new elements “custom metrics“ due to the importance of representing the data quality in a standardized manner when evaluating the potential publication and sharing of the data.

To represent the relationship between the internal and external components of the DATAMITE architecture, **Figure 32** shows the moment in the session describing the quality indicators as metadata meaning the value of data and facilitating data interoperability for the sharing process

when publishing data into different target ecosystems such as IDSA dataspace, Gaia-X, European Portals, and Data Markets. DATAMITE considers data products as core elements and the quality indicators are key. For the specific case of GAIA-X, a tool has been developed for adapting the DATAMITE Data Product to the GAIA-X compliant Data product.

Figure 32. Screenshot During the Data Quality in Data Spaces Session – DATAMITE’s Approach

Related Data Space Projects and Initiatives: Table 10 displays the data space initiatives and projects as well as the collaborating or participating partners to present an overview about the engagement in those. The following paragraphs then provide a more in-depth look about the activities of DATAMITE partners concerning related data space project and initiatives, providing information about our contributions and impact to them.

Data Space Initiative/Project	Collaborating/Participating DATAMITE Partner(s)
AD4GD	PSNC
AgriDataSpace	1001 Lakes, PSNC
AgriFoodTEF	PSNC
DATA CELLAR	CERTH, E-REDES, HEDNO

Data Space Initiative/Project	Collaborating/Participating DATAMITE Partner(s)
Data Spaces Alliance Finland	1001 Lakes
Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC)	CERTH, TECNALIA
EDDIE	E-REDES
ENERSHARE	E-REDES
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	EGI
Gaia-X	ITI, CERTH, EGI, HEDNO, PSNC, TECNALIA
Green Deal Data Space (GDDS)	1001 Lakes, EGI, PSNC
International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)	ITI, 1001 Lakes, CERTH, HEDNO, TECNALIA
Trusted European Media Data Spaces (TEMS)	1001 Lakes
OMEGA-X	E-REDES
Pontus-X	PSNC
SYNERGIES	E-REDES, HEDNO
DEPLOYTOUR	ITI
BDVA	ITI
EUCAIM	ITI

Table 10. Data Spaces and Participants

1001 Lakes is deeply involved in the integration and effectiveness of data spaces. Their collaboration with the DSSC has been a critical aspect of their contributions, ensuring that the tasks they undertake are well-coordinated and impactful.

In the AgriDataSpace CSA project, 1001 Lakes played a vital role by providing specifications of the Common European Agricultural Data Space and leading the Roadmap in WP4. Their expertise also extends to the Trusted European Media Data Spaces (TEMS) project, where they

serve both as a technical data space expert and contribute to legal and governance discussions, showcasing their multifaceted approach to data space challenges.

As an active member of the IDSA since 2020, 1001 Lakes co-chairs the IDSA Rulebook Working Group, influencing the development of standards and practices within data spaces. In April 2024, they launched the Expert Group 10: DSSC Rulebook Tool, which they coordinate, focusing on creating practical tools for data space governance and management.

Furthermore, 1001 Lakes is a member of the DSSC SSF, where they regularly participate and contribute as one of the few SME members, enhancing data space strategies at a higher level. They are also involved in drafting the next DSSC Discussion Paper, due in Fall 2024, which will explore the implications of Generative AI in data spaces.

One of their team members is seconded through MyData Global as an employee at the DSSC, focusing on stakeholder interactions, the DSSC Blueprint, glossary, and building blocks such as data space intermediary or operator. The company was also involved in founding both the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) and the Data Spaces Alliance Finland.

Looking forward, 1001 Lakes aims to create and publish the first version of the DSSC Rulebook Tool in 2024, based on the existing frameworks of the Sitra Fair Data Economy Rulebook and the IDSA Rulebook. They also plan to encourage broader contributions from DATAMITE experts to further improve the work of the Expert Group.

Their participation in thematic groups focused on governance, business, and technology shapes the evolving landscape of data spaces further, ensuring that not only technical requirements are addressed but also broader organizational and governance aspects that impact the data space ecosystem.

CERTH is contributing significantly to data preparation, anonymization, and consumption within the context of data spaces. They are developing tools that facilitate the preparation of valuable and shareable data products, thereby ensuring transparency in data exchange within data spaces, contributing to data anonymity, and exploring identity management within the DATAMITE framework, along with aligning it with the certification process on the IDS connectors.

First, CERTH is designing and developing a tool to transform datasets into data products. This tool provides various functionalities, such as data analysis and processing to deliver valuable insights, aggregation of datasets from multiple sources, and extraction of dataset subsets. Additionally, it ensures that the data products adhere to data space standards for seamless sharing.

Moreover, they are working on a tool to track transactions during the data-sharing process within data spaces. This tool logs all actions between a Data Provider and a Data Consumer, including access requests, data agreements, and data transfers. By recording these interactions, the tool aims to enhance transparency and integrity in data sharing.

CERTH is also developing an anonymization tool to protect sensitive information within datasets while maintaining their utility when shared in data spaces. The tool identifies sensitive columns in the imported dataset, allowing users to select the desired columns and choose the appropriate anonymization technique for each. Furthermore, CERTH will ensure fine-grained access control and explore integrating identity management within the DATAMITE framework with IDSA components, considering their specific authentication mechanisms.

As part of pilot 3, CERTH acts as a data consumer within DATA CELLAR, which is an energy data space, and as a service provider for HEDNO. This dual role enables CERTH not only to utilize data from the data space but also to contribute to it for other participants.

Looking ahead, CERTH aims to continue developing useful tools for the data sharing process and maintain active participation in data space initiatives. These future goals are designed to further enhance the capabilities and effectiveness of data sharing and utilization across various sectors.

CERTH has also actively participated in several key data space projects, including DATA CELLAR, IDSA, EDC, and GAIA-X. This involvement contributes to shaping the future landscape of data management and sharing at a global level.

EGI is co-leading the design and development of DATAMITE Connectors to EU Portals and Data Markets, currently looking for an external solution to replace the EOSC Marketplace, which was suspended by the EC, with an unforeseen situation currently under discussion under the EOSC Beyond project. In addition to this, EGI is contributing on exploring and optimizing data monetization strategies and the data value beyond the economic value.

Furthermore, EGI has participated in the Green Deal Data Space and is an active member of EOSC and GAIA-X as well as the DSSC Blueprint Building Blocks Legal, Data Sovereignty and Trust, and Data Value Creation.

Moreover, EGI participates in the monthly DSSC Thematic Group Meetings on Business Models, where EGI has been collecting insights and potential collaboration with other industry experts to enhance business strategies within data spaces.

E-REDES actively contributed to the Energy Data Spaces Policy Paper published by the ETIP-SNET in January 2024, with the objective to identify the main opportunities and use cases for the data spaces implementation in the energy sector. Furthermore, E-REDES analysed the work being performed on the five Horizon Europe projects on Energy Data Spaces (DATA CELLAR, EDDIE, ENERSHARE, OMEGA-X, SYNERGIES) to evaluate the creation of synergies with the DATAMITE project and to explore the utilisation of the data spaces being developed in these projects as endpoints to pilot 4.

E-REDES, together with HEDNO, TECNALIA, ITI and CERTH, established some initial promising contacts with the DATA CELLAR and OMEGA-X projects and plans to continue the collaboration with them to potentially utilise their data spaces as endpoints for pilot 4. Additionally, E-REDES aims to develop a focused ecosystem strategy for the energy sector centred on data spaces, which is likely to enhance collaboration and innovation across the industry. Their collaboration with key data space projects such as OMEGA-X and DATA CELLAR helps advancing data space initiatives within the energy sector, thereby broadening the impact of these initiatives, and enhancing their capabilities in integrating as well as leveraging data space technologies.

HEDNO is actively contributing to pilot 3, focusing on sharing company data with project partner CERTH via a data space, specifically utilising the DATAMITE framework and DATA CELLAR. This collaboration is crucial as it enables HEDNO to navigate and address the complexities involved in data sharing, especially for demanding use cases such as the simulation and optimization of distribution network operations.

The impact of HEDNO's involvement is extensive, both externally and internally. Externally, the company identifies challenges and develops solutions concerning data sharing for critical operations. Internally, HEDNO gains valuable experience through its participation in the project, enhancing its understanding and capabilities in areas such as data spaces, data governance, and business strategies. Looking ahead, HEDNO's future objectives include continuing to share data through DATA CELLAR and potentially expanding to include a GAIA-X compliant data space. This proactive approach aims to enhance data interoperability and governance within the energy sector.

HEDNO's participation in key data space Projects, such as SYNERGIES, along with its intention to explore the capabilities offered by DATA CELLAR, GAIA-X compliant data spaces, and the IDSA ecosystem, enhances their expertise and enables them to participate in implementing innovative data-sharing frameworks within the energy sector.

IDSA is taking on a critical role in the standardization, adoption, and promotion of data spaces. Their involvement in the DSSC initiative is particularly noteworthy as it establishes a vital connection between DATAMITE and the broader data space community. This strategic engagement ensures that DATAMITE remains in sync with the evolving trends in the data space sector and effectively utilises DSSC resources.

Beyond individual projects, IDSA's influence extends across more than ten projects, with their active participation in DSSC potentially impacting many others. This comprehensive engagement not only broadens IDSA's reach within the data space ecosystem but also facilitates the advancement and harmonisation of data space standards across various sectors and initiatives. Through these efforts, IDSA plays a significant role in shaping the future of data management and utilisation within an increasingly interconnected digital environment.

Further DATAMITE related tasks where IDSA is involved with a significant effort include a significant part of the Task 1.4 outcome, reflected on the deliverable 1.2, was inspired by the DSSC building blocks³ and the collection of standards and technologies landscape⁴. Then, the execution of task 2.1, which fully aligned to Blueprint 0.5 and subsequently Blueprint 1.0.

And finally, the contribution to tasks 6.4 (Coordination with the Data Spaces Support Centre and related Data Spaces), and 6.5 (Ecosystem Development and Community Building).

ITI has its focus on the management of data within the companies, preparing it before it is shared. The goal is that data has a highly adherence to FAIR principles, is rich in metadata that enhances its findability and interoperability, and it has great quality. To this purpose, ITI leads the development of components like the metadata repository or the data governance backend, that will provide content to user interfaces like the data catalogue or the glossary, as well as to tools like the data product composition. In addition, ITI is highly involved in the data quality module as well as leading two of the support tools, related with data discovery, and data ingestion and storage. These later components will allow for the addition of new datasets into the framework, regardless of whether they are stored within or remotely in other databases. In a nutshell, the

³ <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE/357074917/Technical+Building+Blocks>

⁴ <https://dssc.eu/space/SE1/185794561/Collection+of+Standards+and+Technologies+landscape+%7C+Version+1.0+%7C+October+2023>

efforts of ITI are focused on assuring that the data that will be shared in data spaces or other initiatives is high value data and highly interoperable.

ITI actively engages in various European and Spanish forums and platforms, significantly contributing to the advancement of data spaces. It collaborates closely with the Directorate of the Spanish Government responsible for data space policies, including the Ministry of Industry and the Spanish Secretariat of Data and AI. As a founding member of the BDVA and a Board of Directors member, ITI coordinates the i-Spaces task force, which has established a federation of experimentation hubs across Europe. ITI is also highly involved in the BDVA's European Data Spaces activities, particularly as the chair of the i-Spaces group, which aims to accelerate data-driven innovation in various industrial sectors. Since late 2021, ITI has participated in the task force TF10 on Data Sharing Spaces, engaging with stakeholders, supporting EC initiatives, and liaising with other key projects. Moreover, ITI holds a position on the Board of Directors for GAIA-X at both European and Spanish national levels and presides over GAIA-X Spain. ITI is also an active member of the International Data Space Association (IDSA) and the Data Space Support Center (DSSC). Within the DSSC, ITI contributes as an expert in the Governance Expert Group and participates in thematic groups focusing on business, governance, and technology contributing on the DSSC Blueprint Building Blocks development, as well as the Strategic Stakeholder Forum.

ITI is involved in several EU Data Spaces projects, such as DATES (European Data Space for Tourism) and EUCAIM (European Federation for Cancer Images), maintains links with the Green Deal Data Space and the Agrifood Data Space. In DEPLOYTOUR project, ITI is developing a trusted and secure Common European Tourism Data Space. This project's outcomes will provide a foundation for governance and policy-making, fostering innovation powered by tourism data and positioning Europe as a premier sustainable living and travel destination. Additionally, ITI collaborates with the Eclipse Foundation on organizing eSSAM 2024, which focuses on data spaces.

PSNC is focusing their contributions within the data space domain on projects such as AgriDataSpace CSA, where they define specifications for CEADS, and AD4GD, a project that is providing building blocks for a Green Deal Data Space aligned with the CSA initiative. Both projects are led in PSNC by Data Analytics and Semantics Department. PSNC's work is integral to promoting semantic interoperability ensuring effective communication and data exchange

across disparate systems (related to Task 2.3). In their roles within AD4GD and DATAMITE, PSNC has successfully deployed, tested, and tailored various data space components. They have set up a demonstrator of EDC connectors at their facility, linked to a MinIO storage backend. PSNC is also evaluating Pontus-X as the foundation for the marketplace required for their pilot implementation. Moreover, they are involved in the onboarding process with Gaia-X, and in leveraging PSNC data harmonization pipelines for datasets that will be made available via the marketplace. PSNC is also involved in the technology thematic group.

Moving forward, PSNC aims to currently working on the deployment and test of the latest version of EDC (v0.7), continue the configuration and customization of Pontus-X, and finalize the Gaia-X onboarding process. These steps are crucial for enhancing the functionality and integration of data space components within their pilot projects. PSNC also actively participates in thematic groups focused on Technology, underscoring their dedication to elevating technical standards and practices within the data space community. Their involvement in data space projects such as AgriDataSpace, AgrifoodTEF, AD4GD, and GAIA-X highlights their dedication in advancing agricultural data space initiatives and associated technologies as well as the broader goals of fostering interconnected and interoperable data ecosystems that support sustainable and efficient agricultural practices.

TECNALIA is delivering substantial contributions to the development of data space technologies and methodologies by creating a data quality model suitable for data spaces, alongside building a support tool designed to facilitate the development of internal data products. This contribution is critical for improving data management and utilisation across various industries. Furthermore, TECNALIA plays a crucial role in fostering data sharing within data spaces, focusing particularly on the onboarding and data transfer processes. They are enhancing the EDC with extensions for transaction registration and enforcement of data usage policies.

Furthermore, TECNALIA is developing a module to streamline the onboarding process for Gaia-X, aiming to improve data interoperability across platforms. Additionally, TECNALIA contributes to the formulation of the IDSA Architecture 5.0, influencing the comprehensive framework that governs data space interactions and integrations. The impact of TECNALIA's efforts is multidimensional, enhancing data quality evaluation and integrating data quality considerations into the data product model.

Moreover, their work facilitates the data space onboarding process for non-technical entities and provides advanced functionalities to improve data sharing processes, observability, and data

sovereignty. Looking ahead, TECNALIA aims to define a DQV extension for the formal definition of quality metrics, a development that will further enrich data quality management and contribute to the robustness of data spaces.

TECNALIA is also an active participant in thematic groups focusing on Business and Governance, emphasizing a comprehensive approach to addressing various aspects of data spaces.

UniKo is focusing on the analysis of contemporary data ecosystems. This exploration is critical as it aids in identifying both technical and organizational challenges linked to ensuring adherence to data space reference architecture models and facilitating data monetization efforts. Going forward, UniKo aims to pinpoint key performance indicators and metrics relevant to data spaces. Moreover, UniKo participates actively in technology-oriented workshops that are related to data spaces, enhancing their technical expertise and contributions within the field.

5.3 Next Steps

Over the past 18 months, the partners involved in the various groups and communities of the DSSC as well as several data space projects and initiatives have been identified, and an initial analysis has been conducted. Thanks to this first phase, we are now in the position to develop an increasingly adapted, targeted strategy. This strategy will enable us to specify the necessary actions to be implemented in the upcoming phases of the project, which will strengthen our engagement and exchange with the DSSC as well as driving the efforts for the deployment of the Common European Data Spaces even further.

Our next steps involve conducting an in-depth survey within the DATAMITE project partners to gather in-depth insights into the specific expertise and extended connections of our partners concerning data spaces and their further involvement in projects and initiatives.

The information will allow us to highlight the contributions and impact of DATAMITE as well as to identify more opportunities for future integrations of the DATAMITE framework in suitable data space projects and extend the reach of DATAMITE even further. This provides more possibilities for feedback, improvements, and an increased number of participants in the thematic groups as well as the general community of the DSSC, expanding their reach and increasing the options for knowledge exchange for all involved parties. Especially the recently published Blueprint material could gain a significantly increased number of readers from this.

At first, the survey aims to assess the levels of expertise of our partners, provide them with helpful resources and guidance such as the DSSC Blueprint to further enhance their expertise, and encourage their engagement with DSSC and beyond. This approach enables more DATAMITE partners to participate in the Expert Groups, the Thematic Groups, and the Strategic Stakeholder Forum. Furthermore, this allows the partners to identify DATAMITE integration opportunities more easily.

Next step is to gather information about direct or indirect connections of DATAMITE partners to data space projects and initiatives that are not yet engaged with DATAMITE. This enables us to identify and embrace even more opportunities for engagement as well as integration that are currently not in the scope of DATAMITE or the DSSC yet.

Finally, this survey will uncover gaps and pain points by identifying hurdles when starting out with data spaces and DATAMITE. This allows us and the DSSC to fix remaining issues, address missing links in the narrative, and clarify uncertainties regarding the benefits of their usage.

6 Ecosystem Development and Community Building Strategy and Activities

6.1 Engagement Strategy

The ecosystem strategy aims to provide a comprehensive exploration of the European landscape, aiming to understand its current state, key players, trends, and prospects. Collaboration among academia, industry, and government is fostered by initiatives and projects, creating an ecosystem where data is the core asset to trade. Furthermore, significant steps are being taken by European countries to address aspects like sovereignty, heterogeneity, monetisation of the data or even aspects that impact the later value chain, such as the fairness of the AI algorithms based on the quality of the data to be consumed. In this manner, and despite the orthogonal dimension to the Data trading and sharing, by ensuring that AI technologies are deployed in a responsible and accountable manner, Europe strives to strike a balance between fostering innovation and safeguarding individual rights, boosting public trust and confidence in AI systems.

By gaining a holistic understanding of the Data landscape in Europe, appreciation can be developed for the data stakeholder's capabilities, collaboration can be fostered through communities of developers of new tools, and avenues for further growth and innovation can be identified.

Table 11 shows the main focus of the ecosystem strategy for DATAMITE is to bootstrap the ecosystem based on the following KPIs:

	Networks of Contact points	10000+	Overall contacts with whom the project will contact to
Ecosystem Building	Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10+ Horizon projects • 4+ EU data infrastructure • Networks • 3 Networks of AI Excellence Centres • 20+ EU DIHs 	Create synergies on joint events, workshops, joint publications, etc.

Table 11. Ecosystem and Community Building KPIs (M36)

To achieve these, the DATAMITE ecosystem development and community building strategy lay on the next actions that describe the tools that the consortium has in place to execute the strategy:

- **The identification and engagement with relevant ecosystems** to build the basis for long-term sustainability by capitalising on those where the partners of the consortium are involved.
- **The contribution and adoption of Open-Source assets**, to engage with a community of developers. The growth of a community of supporters around DATAMITE components will guarantee a long-term sustainability plan to extend those more appealing to this community over the upcoming years, evolving the current technological choices with new – and future – technologies and standards.
- **The establishment of joint activities with EU partnerships, associations**, and other networks / working groups will provide visibility across strategic research labs and companies for early adopters of the technology.

To execute these, the strategy has been divided by stakeholders (Section 6.1.1) and phases (Section 6.1.2).

6.1.1 Target Stakeholders

The main strands have been identified and target the four actors that DATAMITE aims to engage with:

- **Developer community**. The main aim is for those who aim to extend components that are currently under testing, in early release, or on continuous development within the DATAMITE framework. This is to be done through the Eclipse Foundation.
- **EU-funded projects relative to Data**. This is an augmentation of the communications and impact of the activities of each of the projects within the cluster. It was initiated at the level of the projects funded in the same call as DATAMITE but with the aim of being extended to newly funded projects relative to Data.
- **Strategic initiatives and strategic projects** that could position DATAMITE as a de-facto data tool for the European landscape.
- **Consumers or final stakeholders**, which are companies and research centres that can be divided by market segments and that DATAMITE consortium pruned – initially – to those that are focused on the use cases of the project.

It is key to have a timely synchronisation between the technical progress of the project components and the engagement with the communities, managing the expectations of the stakeholder to communicate with but providing an adequate onboarding mechanism supported by the outcomes of the project as they are being produced. This means that for example, a final

consumer of the DATAMITE technology working on the agricultural or marine sector will aim to have a final product relatively mature to work with, while in the case of research labs or developers might see the potential behind the tools provided by DATAMITE and decide to extend these in case a functionality is not yet implemented – or apart from the existing roadmap of development.

6.1.2 Ecosystem Building Strategy Phases

The Ecosystem Development strategy outlines the systematic approach for developing and nurturing the DATAMITE community. It is divided into three distinct phases (**Figure 33**), each with specific goals and activities designed to foster collaboration, enhance capacity, and ensure the sustainability of the DATAMITE framework in the long term. This phased approach ensures a structured and efficient progression from planning and stakeholder engagement to infrastructure development, collaboration, capacity building, and, ultimately, the expansion and sustainability of the ecosystem.

Figure 33. The Three Phases of the Ecosystem Development Strategy

Phase 1: Initial (M6-M11)

The first phase of the strategy focuses on identifying key trends and leading organisations and stakeholders. This involves conducting a thorough needs assessment and stakeholder analysis to identify the specific requirements and expectations of various groups involved in the project, while also analysing the European Data Ecosystem for a seamless market placement. This phase is executed while the technical advancement of the project is on early stage.

Phase 2: Development (M12-M29)

The second phase, which matches most of the development stage of the DATAMITE framework, concentrates on building the infrastructure necessary for the ecosystem’s development and

success by shifting the focus towards fostering collaboration and enhancing the capacity of stakeholders with various collaborative events, workshops, and seminars. Moreover, this phase also prioritises the publication and dissemination of the project's results and best practices, enabling external stakeholders to learn from successful case studies and adopt proven strategies in their own initiatives, as well as fostering the early adoption of the framework. Furthermore, the community of developers is initiated through Eclipse Foundation providing the support for these openly contribute to the existing components.

Phase 3: Maturity (M30-M36)

During the third phase of the Ecosystem strategy, the maturity of the project will be assessed, with emphasis on the utility of the outputs of DATAMITE with respect to future exploitation and re-use. From these outputs, the focus will be on the engagement with connected projects and initiatives, evaluating plant and potential synergies, while cultivating joint activities with organizations having the potential to enter formal collaboration.

In the following section, the specific actions undertaken for the development of these phases are described, as well as the future activities foreseen for the rest of the project's development.

6.2 Key Strategy Activities during the Initial Phase

As of June 2024 (M18), the Initial phase activities (Phase 1) of the Ecosystem building strategy was completed (in M11) while the Development phase (Phase 2) is currently in progress (from M12-Today) as described in Section 6.1.2.

Activities executed on Phase 1 are shown below in section 6.2.1.

6.2.1 Collection of Information from Existing EU DATA Projects

A collection of projects under Data topics was performed on the funded projects of [Cordis database](#) from 2010 until 2023. The collection seeks to look for the most influential organisations during the last years on the topic, and also to be able to find the most relevant collaborators of these. The taxonomies and vocabularies used for the navigation of this collection was extracted from the European Commission portal. The dataset has been publicly shared at the [ZENODO open repository](#). Furthermore, a small UX on Python was constructed on top of the data for the partners of the consortium to get insights on the information collected and on visual bases. The **Figure 34** depicts the search mechanism on the countries more successful depending on where the projects are funded. It also shows the Ecosystem compass access.

The **Figure 34** shows, on a single diagram, the connections between projects and topics, based on the stakeholder type – SME, large company, research organisation, public bodies, higher or secondary education, and other and the connections by research or market topic. These topics were extracted from CORDIS taxonomy.

Figure 34. Interactive Ecosystem Navigator Front-end

Figure 35. Interactive Ecosystem Navigator - European Projects filtered by Research Topic and Organisation Type

Finally, we filtered the different organisations cooperating across projects and the number of projects that an organisation has in common with the others. Organisations can be also

categorised by amount of funding obtained from projects on data individually. This means that they have a relative strong expertise and knowledge on the topics. This information can be searched based only on a specific country. The top organisations at European level can be seen in the **Figure 36**.

Organization Name	EU funds	City	Country
Max-planck-gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Wissenschaften Ev	302,020,547.33	MUNCHEN	
Commissariat A L Energie Atomique Et Aux Energies Alternatives	249,387,462.41	PARIS 15	
Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung Ev	227,737,628.48	MUNCHEN	
Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique Cnrs	134,829,034.58	Paris	
Deutsches Zentrum Fur Luft - Und Raumfahrt Ev	109,180,839.07	KOLN	
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	109,081,596.59	ROMA	
Forschungszentrum Julich Gmbh	104,498,674.91	JULICH	
Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	97,972,593.96	THERMI THESS...	
Agenzia Nazionale Per Le Nuove Tecnologie, L'energia E Lo Sviluppo Ec...	93,031,157.70	ROMA	
Stichting Radboud Universitair Medisch Centrum	89,241,298.67	Nijmegen	
Karlsruher Institut Fuer Technologie	88,879,886.96	Karlsruhe	
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	82,647,177.48	Leuven	
Interuniversitair Micro-electronica Centrum	81,669,348.04	Heverlee	
Technische Universiteit Delft	79,286,156.86	Delft	
Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus Vtt Oy	75,657,273.26	Espoo	

Figure 36. Organisations Ranked by Amount of Funding Landed on EU DATA Projects (2010- 2023)

In addition, the **Figure 37** show the top collaborators within the context of the most successful organisations in the landscape of European Data.

Figure 37. Ecosystem Tool - Most Frequent Partners in European DATA Consortia

A total of 14.649 organisations have been collected and a directory of contacts have been placed to the partners working on the ecosystem activities of the DATAMITE consortium to develop or contact the projects based on their needs. **Figure 38** shows how the data is placed in a map and by clicking on one of the organisations, the information that can be accessed from them – as per CORDIS platform.

Figure 38. The Ecosystem Tool Map for European DATA Coordinators & Participants

6.2.2 Market Analysis

A market analysis has been conducted together with the WP4 – Task 4.1 Strategies to improve data monetization in EU Companies – extracting the value proposition . In addition, this market analysis has been done to have a better understanding on the target stakeholders and the

message to effectively engage them as well as to having a broader understanding on the current picture of the European Data market.

These insights are reported in the **Deliverable D4.1**.

6.2.3 Leveraging on the Networks of the DATAMITE Partners

During the Phase 1 and initial months of Phase 2, an analysis of DATAMITE's stakeholders' interests and potentials for their role as ecosystem development contributors was conducted through 1 to 1 meetings between the task leader of T6.5 and the representatives of the organisations, acting as main actors in the Ecosystem development activities (IDSA, ECL, E-REDES, ITI, ZSI). These meetings aimed to understand each partner's interest and potential benefits from the ecosystem while also discussing courses of action. The main outcome was the alignment and understanding on the dissemination of results. In addition, it was key to coordinate the engagement to avoid overstressing existing channels. E.g., the ongoing collaboration between E-REDES and IDSA for engaging the European Energy Data ecosystem through IDSA working groups and networking channels specifically oriented to the Energy data marketplace.

6.2.4 Community of Developers and Open-Source DATAMITE

The subsection describes the process for engagement, guidelines and infrastructure that the DATAMITE project has put in place to host its open-source code and to manage its interactions with early adopters, along with supporting open-source best practices such as transparency, openness, meritocracy, and vendor neutrality.

6.2.4.1 Open-source Governance and the Eclipse Development Process

Professional open-source projects are governed according to certain rules, processes, and best practices to manage contributions and development by diverse communities. This is especially important for vendor-neutral open-source projects which are not managed by a single entity. The aim for DATAMITE open-source assets is to become community-driven, vendor-neutral open-source projects.

The Eclipse Development Process defines the processes and rules, governance structures and definitions, project roles, releases and reviews, and interaction between projects and the community⁵.

The very basis for setting up a successful open-source project with proper governance is the project creation. The following figure shows the process of project creation at the Eclipse Foundation.

Figure 39. The Eclipse Project Creation Process

It starts with a proposal describing the project, the content of the code, the license used, the project leader and the first committers. The proposal is made available to the community for review for two weeks. At the end of the community review period, the creation review begins with a trademark review. After the creation review, the project is created, and provisioning can begin, i.e., moving the code to the Eclipse Foundation infrastructure and ensuring that the committer's paperwork is in place (contributor/committer agreements). After the project is provisioned, an Intellectual Property (IP) review is performed to identify potential issues such as missing copyrights, copying code, or incompatible licenses between dependencies or with the license

⁵ <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/>

selected by the project. Finally, once the IP review is complete, the initial contribution is released and can be safely shared.

The initial contribution when creating a new project consists of a piece of code of various sizes and may belong to a single organisation or different organisations. Contributing a single piece of code for a single organisation is straightforward and takes between 2 weeks and two months for the creation and the IP review. Conversely, in the case of a large piece of code and/or many contributors from different organisations, which is the case for a research project, this exercise can take a lot of time and effort. In such a context, the Eclipse Foundation has found that this can slow down the project, which is not desirable as the task usually occurs in the last few months of the research project.

Therefore, we have adapted the project creation process to research projects, allowing project partners to get used to open-source best practices and account for the research and development tasks performed during a research project. Eclipse Research Labs aims to prepare research results gradually and continuously to become proper open-source projects during the research project's lifetime.

6.2.4.2 Open-Source Support for Developers: The Eclipse DATAMITE Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab), analysis, and training to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results. In concrete terms, this means enabling:

- **Open Collaboration:** An open infrastructure (GitLab) has been provided for the DATAMITE consortium to collaborate in the open early, which is one of the main guidelines for doing open source successfully in research projects. It also enables good practices of (open source) software development, such as integrating often and soon, automating the process with continuous testing and integration scripts to identify bugs or broken APIs (Application Programming Interface) as early as possible. Lastly, it helps identify the parts of the project that will be open source, they are hosted in the infrastructure, those for which the decision has not yet been taken and those that will not. In this way, the consortium does not discover at the last-minute which components may have an impact on the chosen exploitation plan.
- **Transparency:** It encourages the consortium to work openly, expressing the development plan clearly and openly throughout the process and expressing your decisions clearly and

transparently, avoiding drowning them in internal emails. It also eases the communication of early project results to external stakeholders.

- **Community Governance:** Contributor Agreements allow us to identify and list the contributors to the open-source project(s) from the beginning. Signing the Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA)⁶ is a prerequisite for pushing code in one of the DATAMITE Research Labs repositories. Further information on why an ECA is required and what it is for can be found in the ECA FAQ⁷.
- **Open-Source Licenses:** It is important to select appropriate licenses for the DATAMITE outputs, depending on the intended means of exploitation. In the “default cases,” this will be EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0, or MIT. As all DATAMITE results should be commercially exploitable, GPL and similar strong copyleft licenses will be avoided or associated with a business-friendly licence as a dual licence.
- **IP Review:** IP reviews help to analyse shared code as early and often as possible to identify potential intellectual property issues, such as missing copyright headers in text and source files, metadata files in repositories or third-party dependencies with incompatible licenses (alternative compatible libraries can be used).

OVH provider hosts the Eclipse Research Labs GitLab in France. It is important for the Eclipse Foundation, which is located in Europe, and for a European research project to be hosted and managed in Europe, following European laws on privacy and data protection.

6.2.4.3 Engagement Strategy: From Developers to DATAMITE Open-Source Ecosystem

The engagement of developers is depicted in **Figure 40** through three phases:

- **Phase 1: Identification of code to open-source (M1 – M12):** The DATAMITE consortium selects the parts of the DATAMITE architecture that are going to be open source. These parts are immediately moved to the Eclipse Research Labs. Additional open-source components can be moved to Research Labs, while any DATAMITE component may be created directly in the Eclipse Research Labs if it is intended to be open-source.

⁶ <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ECA.php>

⁷ <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ecafaq.php>

- Phase 2: Open collaboration development (M7 – M36):** During this phase, research and development take place, and the implementation of open-source best practices and governance principles (transparency, openness, IP analyses, contributor agreements) are ensured.
- Phase 3: Eclipse project creation (M24 – beyond project):** When the consortium decides to release a component (or a set thereof) as a vendor-neutral open-source project, the process of moving the project to become a “real” Eclipse Foundation project can be kicked off (as described in section 6.2.4.1). Thanks to the Research Labs approach, the necessary open-source good practices are already in place, so this step will, in most cases, be very smooth.

The indicated timings of the phases are a rough estimate. Usually, the phases overlap due to the quite agile nature of research projects and the diversity of parties involved.

Figure 40 shows an indicative timeline based on the main DATAMITE outputs related to open source.

Figure 40. Eclipse Research Labs Phases

In M5, the Eclipse DATAMITE Research Labs was effectively put in place and provided to the partners for preparing training and other materials according to the timeline shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41. DATAMITE Open-Source Timeline

6.3 Key Strategy Activities during Development – Phase 2

6.3.1 Contribution to Strategic Events

Contributing to the communication and dissemination activities with a focus on engagement with specific organisations: **DATAWEEK 2023**, **EBDVF 2023**, **ADRF2023**, **Data Spaces Symposium 2024**. These events can be seen in the **Section 4.5**.

In addition, and to be more concrete on the engagement with the community of developers that are a key strand for the future sustainability of the outcomes, the activities performed during the first half of the project focused on these, and the rationale behind these actions are:

- Article in **Eclipse Foundation newsletter**: in July 2023, an article explaining the benefits of DATAMITE project was published in the Eclipse [newsletter](#): This newsletter reaches 250.000 recipients.
- **Presentation in EBDVF**: At the session organised by IDSA (Unlocking Interoperability: Harnessing the Dataspace Protocol in Research Projects and Sustainability via Open Source Ecosystems) during the EBDVF event in Valencia in October 2023, where DATAMITE project was presented among others, Michael Plagge (VP Business Development at the Eclipse Foundation) introduced the EDWG (under construction in that

moment) and explained how to contribute to the EDC or other open source projects from a research project.

- **eSAAM 2024 conference:** DATAMITE is sponsoring and co-organising the eSAAM conference, a scientific conference which will take place in October 2024 in Mainz, Germany, collocated with the OCX conference (Open Community experience, <https://www.ocxconf.org>) and whose main topic this year is Dataspaces. ITI is collaborating with ECL in the organization of this ACM conference.
- At the time of writing, an article for the **Eclipse Foundation newsletter** is being written. This article is planned to be published on June 28th, 2024, along with a different article about the EDWG, the EDC and the EDP, with the aforementioned goal of creating a connection and engaging with the community behind these projects.

6.3.2 Synergies with EU Funded Projects related to Data Monetization

The organisations IDC and ITI have a close relationship as a result of previous projects and initiatives. During the Data Week 2023, they began discussions to explore potential synergies. At this edition of Data Week, projects funded under the same topic as DATAMITE were invited by the organisation to present their projects. IDC and ITI saw this as a perfect opportunity to share knowledge and align efforts with the project sisters. Consequently, they started conversations with the representatives of FAME, UPCAST, PISTIS, and DATAMITE projects present at the event. The goal was to join forces and participate together in the EBDVF 2023 in Valencia. This joint participation involved a shared booth (with space for each project) and a joint session.

The main action carried out by the projects together has been in all major data events (**Figure 42**):

- [Data week 2023](#)
- [EBDVF 2023](#)
- [Data Space Symposium 2024](#)

Figure 42. Snapshots from EU Project Synergies during Events

During these coordination meetings, the representatives of the four projects found it beneficial to extend their collaboration beyond these events. Therefore, they decided to create an alliance focused on data monetisation, enabling the four projects to collaborate in various areas, not just dissemination. This alliance would also be open to other projects or initiatives related to data monetisation in Europe.

Figure 43. Monthly Alliance Coordination Meetings

As a result, several meetings (**Figure 43**) have been held to steer this initiative. Currently, ITI is coordinating this alliance and has developed an initial proposal, which is being refined to guide the alliance's work. The **main objective** of the alliance is to facilitate collaboration between European projects (**Figure 44**) working on technologies and solutions for data trading, monetising, exchange, and interoperability, aligning our efforts to maximise the impact of our projects. The projects involved in the alliance are:

Figure 44. Projects Participating in the Alliance Activities

The name of the alliance is being determined among several options proposed by the projects. The projects have identified one representative per pillar from each project participating in the recurring meetings of the alliance. This person is the liaison between the project and the alliance on each topic. Then, this person informs the project about proposed actions within the alliance but also, this person informs the alliance in case any collaboration idea arises in each project and involves the projects of the alliance. The main pillars identified for the alliance's work are displayed in **Figure 45**.

Figure 45. Alliance's Main Pillars

We are working on the identification of the specific common objectives in each fundamental pillar and the main actions to carry out during the next months, also the alliance is planning the development of a common branding of the alliance and the possibilities of a common website.

6.3.3 Engagement with Community of Developers and Open-Source

Once the guidelines and infrastructure were put in place in Phase 1 for DATAMITE for the partners to host its open-source code and to manage its interactions with early adopters – as described in **section 6.2.4** – several training sessions were organised with the partners developing technical components in the DATAMITE consortium in order to test the strategy for developers but also to bootstrap the community. These sessions were:

- Open-Source Ecosystem, Open Collaboration, in November 2023. One-hour training in person during the DATAMITE plenary meeting in Bologna, Italy.
- Intellectual Property and Licences in the Context of European Projects⁸, in April 2024. One-hour online workshop by Wayne Beaton, Director of Open-Source Projects at Eclipse Foundation, as part of the EUCloudEdgeIoT⁹ Initiative.
- Open-Source Licensing and Compliance in May 2024. One-hour training in person during the DATAMITE plenary meeting in Poznan, Poland.

Implementing following best practices enable the project partners to work in a professional open-source environment - based on proven Eclipse Foundation practices – and ease the transition from research results into open-source projects. Furthermore, this approach gives the consortium the room to experiment and define the scope of the resulting open-source projects.

⁸ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/event/intellectual-property-and-licences-in-the-context-of-european-projects>

⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

Currently, 36 developers have signed the Contributor Agreement and joined the DATAMITE GitLab repository in Eclipse Research Labs, which can be seen in **Figure 46**.

Figure 46. The DATAMITE Eclipse Labs Repository

The **Figure 46** also shows the initial repositories created by the partners where they commit their prototypes and code to the open repository. This methodology facilitates a collaborative development and following open-source best practices. It is important to remark that most DATAMITE sub-repositories with code contain an open-source license that developers would like to apply to their code, also avoiding future incompatibilities between these, license compliance and third-party IP checks. Thus, the development started at M7, is aiming to create an initial snapshot of the DATAMITE platform at the first intermediate release at M20.

7 Next Steps

The primary objective of communication and dissemination is to share project results with stakeholders and transfer acquired knowledge. In the second half of the project, as DATAMITE's results and technologies mature, the partners will intensify their efforts to ensure all stakeholders are informed about project outcomes and activities.

From M19 to M36, the following activities will be amplified:

- Participation in events: DATAMITE will continue to events, Conferences and Workshops / Webinars presenting results, showcasing project achievements and engaging directly with the stakeholders.
- Peer-reviewed publications: Building on the six publications (**Table 4**) already published, DATAMITE will continue submitting papers, focusing on final results and making them available to stakeholders. There are currently 5 publications under preparation and planned for July (by the DATAMITE consortium), August (by TEC, ITI) and October (by TEC, ZSI).
- Social media campaigns and blog posts: In the next 18 months, the focus will shift from introducing the project to highlighting its technical achievements through targeted campaigns and blog posts in close collaboration with technical WPs. Meetings with WP leaders will be organised to schedule content creation.
- Online presence: Efforts will be dedicated to increase the online community of by the project's end. To achieve this, the project will diversify social media campaigns, amplifying joint activities with clusters and initiatives.
- Coordinate with the DSSC further and collect data on partner expertise in data spaces, enhance engagement, extend DATAMITE's impact, identify opportunities, provide the material to the identified stakeholder groups, and improve the onboarding process for future participants to achieve a broader community involvement.
- For the ecosystem building, to continue executing the Phase 2 and start with Phase 3: when appropriate. In the strategy, it is already in the roadmap to define the messages for engagement with strategic partners - IDS, BDVA, ADRA; the detailed list of components to engage with developers – ECL, EGI, and companies; and to keep executing the joint activities to strengthen the engagement among other projects that are focused on DATA – clusters of projects and working groups.

8 Conclusions

This report provides a comprehensive overview of DATAMITE's communication, dissemination, and engagement activities during the first 18 months of the project. It highlights the project's commitment to building a strong and engaged stakeholder community, fostering collaboration, and maximising the impact of its research and development efforts. It demonstrates that DATAMITE has successfully established a robust communication and dissemination strategy, encompassing a range of activities, including:

- **Branding:** The project has developed a strong visual identity, including a logo, branding guidelines, and official templates for presentations and documents, ensuring a consistent and professional appearance across all communication channels.
- **Promotional Materials:** DATAMITE has created various promotional materials, including printed materials (roll-ups, posters, brochures) and multimedia materials (videos, clips, presentations), to effectively communicate project objectives and achievements to a diverse audience.
- **Digital Channels:** The project leverages various digital channels, including a dedicated website, social media platforms, an open-access repository (Zenodo), and a newsletter, to reach a wider audience and facilitate information sharing.
- **Publications:** DATAMITE has published scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals and communicated publications to raise awareness about the project's impact and potential.
- **Events:** The project has actively participated in and hosted events, workshops, and webinars, providing opportunities for direct engagement with stakeholders and fostering collaboration.

DATAMITE is committed to aligning with the broader European Data Ecosystem by actively engaging with the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) and related Data Spaces initiatives. This engagement takes various forms, including:

- **Participation in DSSC Expert Groups:** DATAMITE partners have been invited to contribute their expertise to several DSSC Expert Groups, focusing on governance, rulebooks, and legal aspects of data spaces. This participation allows DATAMITE to directly influence the development of best practices and guidelines for data space implementation.

- **Contribution to DSSC Thematic Groups:** DATAMITE partners actively participate in DSSC Thematic Groups, engaging in discussions and knowledge sharing on topics like the business of data spaces, governance, and technology. This involvement ensures that DATAMITE remains informed about emerging trends and challenges within the data space landscape.
- **Collaboration with related Data Space projects:** DATAMITE partners are actively involved in various data space projects/initiatives, including AgriDataSpace, AD4GD, DATA CELLAR, EDDIE, ENERSHARE, and Gaia-X. This collaboration allows DATAMITE to leverage existing data space infrastructure, test its framework in real-world scenarios, and contribute to developing interoperable data spaces across different sectors.

DATAMITE recognises the importance of building a sustainable ecosystem for its technologies and outputs. This includes:

- **Identifying and engaging with relevant stakeholders:** DATAMITE has conducted extensive research to identify key stakeholders within the European Data Ecosystem, including research institutions, industry players, government agencies, and data space initiatives. The project aims to engage with these stakeholders through targeted communication, participation in relevant events, and collaboration opportunities.
- **Fostering a community of developers:** The project has established a dedicated platform for open-source contributions and actively engages with the Eclipse Foundation to ensure the long-term sustainability of its open-source components.
- **Creating synergies with other initiatives:** DATAMITE seeks to collaborate with other EU-funded projects, associations, and networks to maximise its impact and leverage existing resources. This includes participating in joint events, workshops, and publications and exploring opportunities for joint research and development activities.

DATAMITE has made significant progress in achieving its outreach goals, with notable achievements in website traffic, social media and community engagement, and publications. It will continue its efforts to reach the ambitious targets set for the project's final phase (M36).